

Dissemination/Communication Plan

Project title: “Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)”.

Project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/188.

Period concerning the plan: 01.02.2026-31.01.2029.

European Union Cohesion Policy Program for 2021–2027 1.1.1. Specific support objective "Strengthening research and innovation capacity and introducing advanced technologies into the common R&D system" 1.1.1.9. "Postdoctoral research."

Summary

The plan for different dissemination/communication activities over the three years of the project's implementation is provided.

Scientific results will be disseminated at international conferences, including the International Scientific Conference of the University of Latvia (LU), the Conference of the Cognitive Science Society, CERE, the European College of Sports Science (ECSS), the Baltic Society of Sport Sciences (BSSS), and an IEEE conference. Self-archiving of the main project results is planned in subject-based open-access repositories, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and LU's repository, as well as on platforms such as ResearchGate and Zenodo. Three original scientific articles will be submitted for publication in scientific journals indexed in Scopus or WoS, including two to Q1/Q2 journals. One project application for an international call (e.g., Horizon Innovative Health Initiative and ERA4Health Partnership) and one application for the Fundamental and Applied Research Projects (FLPP) call will be submitted. An AI-driven platform for face (nonverbal) and voice (verbal) recognition will be developed and tested to improve emotion regulation, stress recovery, performance, and well-being for athletes. It will be available as open access for academic (noncommercial) use and archived in Zenodo. To maximize visibility, posts will also be published on the LU website (<https://www.lu.lv/en/>). For a wider audience, information will be regularly provided on the postdoctoral Dr. Behnam Boobani's LinkedIn profile.

1. Objectives

- Dissemination of results;
- Communication;
- Knowledge and data management and protection.

2. Work planned for each year

Year 1

- Posts on the website of LU;
- Poster with project information on the workplace of post-doctorate;
- 1 report at an international conference with an oral presentation at the International Scientific Conference of the University of Latvia and 1 report at an international conference with an oral presentation at the Baltic Society of Sport Sciences (BSSS);
- 1 review paper will be submitted for publication in scientific journals in the Scopus or WoS databases;
- Self-archiving of project results (posters, papers, and annual reports) in subject-based repositories (e.g., *ResearchGate*, *Zenodo*);
- Regular updating of *LinkedIn* profile for the dissemination of project results to a wide audience;
- Attendance of local seminars, conferences, and other public events (e.g., *European Researchers' Night*).

Year 2

- Posts on the website of LU;
- 1 report at an international conference with oral presentation at the International Scientific Conference of the University of Latvia and 1 report at an international conference with oral presentation at the Conference of the Cognitive Science Society;
- Self-archiving of project results (posters, papers, and annual reports) in subject-based repositories (e.g., *ResearchGate*, *Zenodo*);
- Regular updating of *LinkedIn* profile for the dissemination of project results to a wide audience;
- Attendance of local seminars, conferences, and other public events (e.g., *European Researchers' Night*).

Year 3

- Posts on the website of LU;
- 1 report at an international conference with oral presentation (e.g., *European College of Sports Science (ECSS)* or *Baltic Society of Sport Sciences (BSSS)*);
- 2 papers will be submitted for publication in scientific journals in the Scopus or WoS databases;
- Prototype v3.0 for emotion regulation platform (face and voice) and stress-recovery profiles of athletes is developed as open access for academic (noncommercial) use and archived in Zenodo;
- Self-archiving of project results (posters, papers, and annual reports) in subject-based repositories (e.g., *ResearchGate*, *Zenodo*);
- Regular updating of *LinkedIn* profile for the dissemination of project results to a wide audience;
- Attendance of local seminars, conferences, and other public events (e.g., *European Researchers' Night*).

3. Planned scientific results

- 3 scientific publications, including at least 2 in Q1-Q2 SCI journals;
- 5 presentations at international scientific conferences;
- AI-driven face and voice recognition platform in Zenodo;
- 1 project application for an international call (e.g., Horizon Innovative Health Initiative and ERA4Health Partnership) and 1 application for the call of Fundamental and Applied Research Projects (FLPP).

4. Deviations from the working plan

Positive deviations from the dissemination/communication work plan are possible to maximize the project's impact.

5. Corrective actions

When appropriate and necessary, all additional and relevant dissemination and communication activities will be included in the project implementation and incorporated into the project work, thereby improving the visibility of project results.

6. Deliverables

D1.1. The dissemination and communication plan is elaborated (M3).